

AN EVALUATION OF THE IMPLEMENTATION AND EFFICACY OF MARKETING STRATEGIES IN DUMAGUETE CITY'S HOTEL INDUSTRY: A FRAMEWORK FOR POST-PANDEMIC MARKETING RECOVERY

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic has presented unprecedented challenges to the hotel industry, particularly impacting establishments in Dumaguete City. However, amidst these adversities, a study aims to explore how hotels in the area have employed marketing strategies to navigate the crisis and lay the groundwork for a resilient recovery. Utilizing a descriptive research approach, the study collected data through questionnaires, interviews, and observations from twenty-four participating hotels. Results tell that despite facing significant hurdles, the majority of these hotels are accredited by the Department of Tourism and maintain a bed capacity of 50 to 99 persons. Despite challenges, they have displayed resilience, maintaining a monthly average occupancy rate of up to 90 percent, reflecting sustained tourist activity. Notably, many hotels have established themselves in the industry, emphasizing their effectiveness and longevity. Marketing strategies have focused on innovative approaches such as local tours, culinary experiences, and wellness activities, driven by personalization to enhance guest satisfaction. Technology adoption, including chatbots and customized emails, has facilitated direct bookings and operational efficiency. Dynamic pricing mechanisms, supported by revenue management systems, have enabled profit optimization and market adaptation. Leveraging social media and content marketing, hotels have enhanced visibility and engagement, aiming for sustainable growth and success in the post-pandemic era.

Keywords: *Pandemic, Hotel Industry, Marketing Strategies, Recovery Framework, Digital Presence*

INTRODUCTION

The world has shifted in unbelievable ways since the pandemic began, and the hotel industry, known for its resilience and agility, has been at the forefront of this transformation. The hotel industry, significantly impacted by COVID-19, requires empirical studies to establish effective marketing strategies that can respond to the pandemic and prepare for recovery. Under Republic Act No. 11469, also known as the Bayanihan to Heal as One Act, the President has the authority to oversee the operations of establishments to reduce the spread of COVID-19 and aid in the recovery of the Philippine economy. Additionally, the Tourism Act of 2009 mandates the Department of Tourism to enforce a comprehensive system of accreditation for tourism enterprises, including hotels and other accommodation establishments.

In the hospitality sector, choosing the right hotel capacity is crucial from a strategic standpoint for stakeholders. Dumaguete City, recognized as the most improved city during the 10th Cities and Municipalities Competitiveness Summit in October 2022, is a fast-growing and competitive town in Negros Oriental. The hotel industry in Dumaguete faced a tremendous crisis during the pandemic, with operations shut down to counter the hazards posed by the virus. Despite this, Dumaguete is home to 33 registered hotels, catering to work, relaxation, official business travel, and excursions, including establishments like Hotel Essencia, Hotel Nicanor, and Bethel Guest House.

During the pandemic, the focus has been on revitalizing marketing strategies for the hotel industry's recovery. The pandemic has drastically altered the demands of the hospitality sector, making it increasingly competitive and highlighting the strategic value of marketing management. Developing a strategic marketing recovery plan is essential for the industry's survival and growth.

This study aims to evaluate how strategic marketing management is implemented and its effectiveness within Dumaguete City's hotel industry. The results will offer guidance to future hotel managers and top executives, particularly in navigating crises like the pandemic. They'll gain crucial understanding into overcoming industry challenges, underscoring the importance of adapting marketing strategies to a constantly evolving landscape.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

To fulfill the study's objectives, the researcher utilized a descriptive correlational design, distributing self-created survey questionnaires to respondents. Using accessible resources, this method shows the nature of the current situation at the time of the study. The researcher used the 4Ps of Marketing Mix in this investigation, focusing on marketing strategies during the post-pandemic. To further validate the results, self-interviews, and observations were undertaken with the identified key participants.

Research Participants

The participants of the study were managers and supervisors in the hotel industry in Dumaguete City. A total of 86 responses were collected by distributing at least five questionnaires to each of the 24 hotels in Dumaguete City. The data collection took place over four working days, from March 16 to March 20, 2024, and from March 29 to April 2, 2024. Additionally, feedback from hotel receptionists on duty was considered for validation purposes to support the study.

Research Locale

The study took place in Dumaguete City, Negros Oriental, known as the City of Gentle People, and a prominent university town. This lovely city in Central Visayas, Region 7, has become a favorite tourist destination, drawing visitors globally. While diving has long been the main attraction, The city government has also emphasized promoting land-based tourist attractions in Dumaguete and Negros Oriental. The city is subdivided into 30 barangays, the smallest political divisions in a Philippine city.

The respondents for the study were visited at their respective hotel establishments and provided with self-made questionnaires, approved by the managing head. Data collection occurred over four working days, from March 16 to March 20, 2024, and from March 29 to April 2, 2024.

Dumaguete, the capital of Negros Oriental, boasts a population of around 125,000 residents., although this number can double or even triple during the daytime. This vibrant city quickly captivates the hearts of its visitors, making it more than just a gateway to nearby tourist destinations.

Data Gathering Procedure

The study took place in Dumaguete City, Negros Oriental, also known as the City of Gentle People and a well-known university town. This charming city, located in Region 7, Central Visayas, has become a popular tourist hotspot, attracting visitors from around the

world. While diving has long been the main attraction, the city government has also focused on promoting land-based tourist attractions in Dumaguete and Negros Oriental. The city is subdivided into 30 barangays, the smallest political divisions in a Philippine city.

To conduct the study, respondents were visited at their respective hotel establishments and provided with self-made questionnaires, approved by the managing head. Data collection occurred over four working days, from March 16 to March 20, 2024, and from March 29 to April 2, 2024. Dumaguete, the capital of Negros Oriental, has a population of approximately 125,000, although this number can double or even triple during the daytime. This vibrant city quickly captivates the hearts of its visitors, making it more than just a gateway to nearby tourist destinations.

Data Analysis Procedure

Frequency distribution was used to calculate the effectiveness of implementation of strategies. Each entry in the table denotes the frequency or count of occurrences of values within specific groups or intervals, providing a summary of the distribution of values in the sample. Weighted mean, on the other hand, accounts for variation in the relative contribution of individual data values to the mean. Percentage analysis aids in determining the proportion of a specific dataset relative to the whole, enabling the establishment of the hotel industry profile.

Pearson's correlation coefficient measures how strong and in what direction two continuous variables are related. This study looks at how the hotel industry profile relates to how marketing strategies are used, and how the level of strategy implementation affects their effectiveness in Dumaguete City's hotel industry. Regression analysis is used to figure out how important current marketing strategies are and how well they're being used in the industry.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher carefully considered ethical considerations in conducting the research, ensuring transparency, informed consent, voluntary participation, confidentiality, and the well-being of the participants. All necessary ethical considerations and protocols for the entire duration of the study were stringently followed. The researcher also maintained the confidentiality of all data obtained, including the support personnel's identity as well as their ratings. Moreover, the researcher secured ethical approval from the Ethical Committee of the University Research Office.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Accreditation with Department of Tourism

Accreditation With the Department of Tourism	Frequency	Percentage
Star Rating (2-5 Star)	35	28.93
Accredited Hotel with Certification	76	62.81
Not Yet Accredited with DOT	10	8.26
For others, please specify	0	0
Total	121	100

The hotel industry in Dumaguete City showcases a high level of compliance with quality and regulatory standards, as demonstrated by the 62.81% accreditation rate from the Department of Tourism (DOT). This significant proportion underscores the industry's commitment to maintaining high standards in service and operations. According to Chen and Chen (2019), accreditation serves as a benchmark for quality assurance, encouraging hotels to adopt best practices in service delivery and operational efficiency. This is corroborated by Mensah and Dei Mensah (2019), who found that accreditation processes prompt hotels to invest in staff training and development, leading to enhanced customer satisfaction and operational effectiveness. Furthermore, Guillet and Kucukusta (2016) highlight that accredited hotels often benefit from preferential treatment in government-led marketing initiatives, increasing their visibility and attractiveness to potential guests, and thereby boosting occupancy rates and revenue.

Recent studies further emphasize the broader benefits of accreditation. Hao, Chon, and Wen (2021) stress that continuous quality assessment and improvement are essential for maintaining high standards in the hospitality industry. This proactive approach not only ensures compliance with current standards but also prepares hotels to meet future needs and expectations of tourists, fostering long-term sustainability and success. Additionally, Yang, Liu, and Li (2020) found that accreditation enhances a hotel's reputation and credibility, which are critical for attracting international tourists. The integration of sustainable practices into hotel operations, as suggested by Sigala (2018), is increasingly important for accreditation, attracting eco-conscious travelers and providing a competitive edge. These insights illustrate that accreditation not only ensures compliance and quality but also drives continuous improvement, marketing advantages, and sustainability, contributing to the robust growth and competitiveness of the hotel industry in Dumaguete City.

Table 2. The extent of Implementation and Level of Effectiveness of Product

A. PRODUCT	SD	WX	RANK	A. PRODUCT	SD	WX	RANK
Consider local tours, wellness activities, and unique	0.81	4.22	3	It provides our guest with services and offerings that are	0.63	4.62	2

experiences beyond standard amenities.				unique, memorable experiences.			
Incorporate preferred room settings, favorite meals, and personalized greetings.	0.90	4.13	4	It personalized the guest experience by embracing individual preferences.	0.67	4.33	3
Using tools like chatbots and customized emails can enhance guest engagement.	1.06	4.30	2	This virtual handholding boosted our hotel booking conversion rates, leading to an increase in direct bookings.	0.50	4.65	1
Use analytics to understand what guests prefer and adjust your offerings accordingly.	1.08	3.81	5	It offered real-time predictions for demand and prices, enabling personalized guest offers and improving efficiency.	0.95	4.02	4
Stay open to change and adapt based on customer needs and expectations.	0.68	4.53	1	It made our hotel responsive to customer needs and continuously refine our acquisition strategies for better results.	0.50	4.65	1
cwx = 4.20 Well Implemented				cwx = 4.45 Very Effective			

Legend: Range	Verbal Description
4.20 – 5.00	Very Well Implemented
3.40 – 4.19	Well Implemented
2.60 – 3.39	Implemented
1.80 – 2.59	Fairly Implemented
1.00 – 1.79	Not Implemented

Legend: Range	Verbal Description
4.20 – 5.00	Very Effective
3.40 – 4.19	Highly Effective
2.60 – 3.39	Effective
1.80 – 2.59	Somewhat Effective
1.00 – 1.79	Not Effective

The table above illustrates the goods and services provided by the hotel industry in Dumaguete City to meet customer needs. The data shows that hotels in Dumaguete City prioritize flexibility and responsiveness to customer demands and expectations, achieving the weighted mean of 4.53 (rank 1). In contrast, the use of analytics to gain insights into customer behavior received the lowest weighted mean of 3.81 (rank 5). According to Shi (2021), factors such as organizational culture, location, brand image, and competition

significantly influence hotel managers' strategic decisions. The model of hotel resilience offers a valuable framework for planning and implementing strategies to address external challenges. In challenging times, hotel managers are advised to adopt a range of innovations targeting both internal management and customer service. For instance, the development of chatbots, as noted by Putri et al. (2019), enhances marketing and customer support by offering increased convenience, reducing service and support costs, enabling personalized marketing, and creating new data collection opportunities.

The effectiveness of the hotel industry's products and services in Dumaguete City is evident from the weighted mean scores. The application of various marketing strategies, with a 4.65 weighted mean, indicates that the industry is keenly attuned to client needs and consistently enhances its marketing efforts. Similarly, the delivery of unique and memorable guest experiences through distinct services and offerings also achieved a weighted mean of 4.65. Lei (2024) emphasizes the importance of service customization, which involves tailoring services to meet the specific needs of individual customers, recognizing them as distinct individuals rather than anonymous service users. This approach aligns with the tourism industry's unique characteristic of being dynamic and adaptable to changing conditions and customer preferences, as highlighted by Siwek et al. (2022). These findings underscore the industry's commitment to continuous improvement and responsiveness to customer needs, which are crucial for maintaining competitiveness and customer satisfaction.

Table 2. The extent of Implementation and Level of Effectiveness of Price

B. PRICE	SD	WX	RANK	B. PRICE	SD	WX	RANK
Tools like revenue management systems can aid this process.	0.82	4.21	3	Adopting dynamic pricing maximized our profits by adjusting rates to meet the current market demand.	0.89	4.16	4
Implement customized pricing according to customer loyalty and booking history. Loyalty programs and exclusive deals for members can help achieve this goal.	0.71	4.45	1	This strategy boosted profitability by enabling us to set prices at the optimal level for each individual, minimizing lost sales during periods of high demand.	0.94	4.16	4
Ensure that all costs, including taxes and service charges, are mentioned during the booking process to avoid customer dissatisfaction later.	0.86	4.45	1	This approach fostered trust with customers by offering price transparency, enabling them to grasp the value they receive and compare it with competitors.	0.60	4.70	1

When pricing other hotel services like spa treatments, dining experiences, and event spaces, consider offering packages or bundled deals to enhance perceived value.	0.82	4.20	4	This strategy allowed our hotel to meet the specific requirements of different clients and enhance customer satisfaction.	0.68	4.44	3
Monitor competitors' pricing strategies and ensure your rates are competitive. Don't just compete on price but differentiate based on the value provided to guests.	0.79	4.28	2	It yielded numerous benefits for hotels, ranging from identifying market opportunities to optimizing operational efficiency.	0.69	4.45	2

cwx = 4.32 Very Well Implemented

cwx = 4.38 Very Effective

The hotel industry excels in implementing personalized pricing strategies, earning a commendable weighted mean of 4.45. Personalized pricing hinges on factors like customer loyalty and booking history. Hotels prioritize transparency during the booking process, disclosing all expenses, including taxes and service fees, to mitigate consumer dissatisfaction (weighted mean = 4.45). However, other hotel services like spa treatments received a lower ranking, with a weighted mean of 4.20. According to Koo et al. (2020), implementing loyalty programs significantly enhances customer satisfaction and loyalty, fostering long-term financial success and strengthening the consumer-brand relationship. Thus, loyalty programs emerge as indispensable tools for cultivating patronage.

The efficacy of the pricing strategy is evident from the data. The transparent inclusion of taxes and service fees at the time of booking, with a weighted mean of 4.70, has been shown to develop customer trust. Transparent pricing allows customers to compare prices with competitors and understand the value they are receiving. However, dynamic pricing, which involves adjusting prices based on market conditions, received the lowest weighted mean of 4.16. Bagchi et al. (2021) suggest that hotels can enhance guest satisfaction and improve revenue by selecting appropriate service designs and managing resource flows effectively. Additionally, Chan et al. (2021) emphasize that customer experiences are both emotional and cognitive. Therefore, monitoring guest requirements, preferences, and perceptions is critical to successfully delivering exceptional guest experiences.

Table 3. The extent of Implementation and Level of Effectiveness of Promotion

PROMOTION	SD	WX	RANK	PROMOTION	SD	WX	RANK
Developing a robust content marketing strategy is essential. To attract potential guests, utilize various mediums such as website	0.81	4.12	3	This strategy has increased our brand awareness, improved customer	0.72	4.20	4

content, blogs, videos, and guides focusing on travel and hospitality.				engagement, and higher website traffic.
Use social media platforms to showcase your hotel's offerings, share guest experiences, and engage with your audience.	0.82	4.49	1	This strategy empowered our hotel to produce and disseminate pertinent content, including promotions, industry news, and engaging trivia, fostering brand awareness among potential customers.
Partner with influencers who align with your brand to reach a wider audience. Ensure the content created is authentic and resonates with the influencer's audience.	1.03	3.31	5	This strategy allowed us to tap into new audiences and establish their brand as a must-visit destination.
Optimize your website and content for search engines by incorporating keywords that potential guests commonly search for, thus boosting visibility.	0.92	4.09	4	It led to more bookings and revenue for the hotel.
Regularly measure the effectiveness of your promotional strategies and be willing to adapt based on what's working and what's not.	0.81	4.43	2	This strategy raised brand visibility, engaged customers, built relationships, and increased revenue.
cxw = 4.09 Well Implemented				cxw = 4.20 Highly Effective

Table 3 illustrates the implementation of promotional strategies by the hotel industry in Dumaguete City. Promotion involves informing customers about the features and advantages of a product. The data indicates that social media use is the most effective promotional strategy, with a weighted mean of 4.49. In contrast, using influencers ranked lowest with a weighted mean of 3.31. According to Krizanova (2019), online marketing communication's broad reach allows advertisements to target a large audience. This approach helps hotels achieve various objectives, such as raising brand recognition, enhancing customer satisfaction and trust, and strengthening brand loyalty.

The effectiveness of these promotional methods is evident in the hotel industry's increased brand visibility, customer engagement, and relationship building, all contributing to higher bookings and revenue, as indicated by the weighted mean of 4.49. Despite the lower ranking of influencer partnerships (weighted mean = 3.60), the interaction facilitated by internet marketing is crucial. Yoga (2019) emphasizes that travelers are significantly influenced by online reviews and comments from previous customers. Potential customers trust reviews from experienced travelers who have already visited the destination more than

those from potential visitors. Albattat (2020) highlights the growing trend of using online social networks to promote goods and services in the hotel sector. This trend underscores the importance of the hospitality industry embracing technological advancements to enhance guest services and provide employees with efficient tools (Legaspi et al., 2023).

Table 4. The extent of Implementation and Level of Effectiveness of Place

PLACE	SD	WX	RANK	PLACE	SD	WX	RANK
Make sure you have a solid online presence on all relevant platforms, including your website, social media, online travel agents, and others.	0.63	4.42	1	It streamlined operations, offered personalized guest services, enhanced communication, and gleaned valuable insights through data analytics.	0.92	4.09	3
Make the booking process seamless, whether it's on your website, mobile app, or through a third-party platform	0.75	4.22	3	Enabled personalized customer service, enhancing the overall guest experience and boosting satisfaction and loyalty.	0.80	4.09	3
Endeavor for consistency in brand messaging and customer experience across all channels.	0.79	4.19	4	It helped our hotel create a strong and memorable brand impression in the minds of your customers	0.68	4.47	2
Consider developing a mobile app for bookings, customer service, and in-stay services	1.14	3.99	5	This strategy of mobile ordering increased efficiency, lowered staff workload, and minimized costs.	0.92	3.99	4
Remember their preferences and provide consistent personalized service across all touchpoints.	0.88	4.37	2	Customized experiences made guests feel valued and appreciated, encouraging their return.	0.68	4.67	1
cwx = 4.24 Very Well Implemented				cwx = 4.26 Very Effective			

A major factor in drawing visitors was the destination's attractiveness, the hotel's accessibility, and its proximity to popular locations. However, the advent of the digital revolution has led to a new understanding of Place. Place now essentially refers to all the channels via which guests interact with the hotel. Ensuring a strong digital presence across all platforms was very well implemented by hotel industries in Dumaguete City. They made sure to remember their guest's preferences and provide consistent personalized services across all touchpoints. According to Lei (2024), by increasing perceived value and emotional connection, personalized service has been beneficial in raising customer happiness, trust,

and loyalty. This is because personalized service differs fundamentally from "one-size-fits-all" service. Personalization of services is especially important for younger generations, who are pickier and actively look for the best deal. A personalized offer is also seen as "special" since it gives the customer a sense of exclusivity and highlights the consideration of the service provider. As a result, the personalization impact is not limited to a single transaction; rather, it may help sustain emotional bonds and foster long-term business-customer relationships.

Concerning the effectiveness of the real location of a service or product, it helped hotel industries in Dumaguete City create a strong and memorable brand impression in their minds. Customized experiences made guests feel valued and appreciated, encouraging their return. The customer's experience should be coherent and consistent regardless of the channel they use to interact with the hotel—website, mobile app, phone call, or in-person visit. Customers' preferences are remembered, previous contacts are acknowledged, and their experience is personalized at every touchpoint via an efficient omnichannel strategy. This seamless omnichannel experience is made possible by data, which is essential. Hotels that track customer visits across many media might obtain significant insights into patron behavior and preferences. By using this data, companies can guarantee consistency over all channels, give tailored recommendations, and enhance the consumer's experience.

According to Böhme (2023), an experience is the result of an individual's perception of a cue, which involves reacting to specific elements and interpreting them afterward. Emotions, meanings, and comprehension influence interpretations of experiences.

Table 5. Summary on the Extent of Implementation and Level Effectiveness on the 4Ps of the marketing mix.

EXTENT OF IMPLEMENTATION	WX	LEVEL OF EFFECTIVENESS	WX
Product	4.20	Product	4.45
Price	4.32	Price	4.38
Promotion	4.09	Promotion	4.20
Place	4.24	Place	4.26
cwx = Very Well Implemented	4.21	cwx = Very Effective	4.32

The implementation of marketing strategies in the hotel industry in Dumaguete City achieved a weighted mean of 4.21, indicating that they are very well implemented. The effectiveness of these marketing strategies received a weighted mean of 4.32, interpreted as very effective. These results suggest that the marketing strategies employed by hotels in Dumaguete City are both crucial and effective. According to Shi et al. (2021), the selection of coping measures by managers is influenced by factors such as organizational culture,

location, brand image, and competitors. The model of hotel resilience provides a valuable framework for planning and selecting strategies to address external challenges.

Recent literature supports the importance of adaptive and innovative strategies in the hospitality industry. For example, Sigala (2018) highlights that dynamic marketing strategies, including the use of social media and personalized marketing, are essential for engaging with customers and building brand loyalty. Furthermore, Hao, Chon, and Wen (2021) emphasize the necessity for hotel managers to adopt a variety of innovations aimed at both internal management and customer service, particularly during challenging times. Innovations such as advanced data analytics and customer relationship management (CRM) systems are crucial for understanding customer preferences and enhancing service delivery (Guillet & Kucukusta, 2016). These strategies not only improve operational efficiency but also increase customer satisfaction and loyalty, contributing to the overall resilience and success of hotel businesses.

Table 6. Relationship between the Profile of Hotel Industry and the Extent of Implementation of Marketing Strategies

Variables	rs	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Type of Accreditation	0.021	0.686	Fail to reject the null hypothesis	Not Significant
Bed Capacity	0.041	0.005	Reject	Significant
Monthly average	0.032	0.041	Reject	Significant
Year of Operation	0.022	0.002	Reject	Significant
Spearman Rank Correlation level of Significant =0.05				

Legend:

<u>Correlation Coefficient</u>	<u>Verbal Description</u>
± 0.00 – ±0.09	<i>negligible</i>
±0.10 – ±0.29	<i>small</i>
±0.30 – ±0.49	<i>medium</i>
±0.50 – ±1.00	<i>large</i>

Source: Miller & Cohen (2001)

Table 6 provides insights into how the hotel industry profile relates to the implementation of marketing strategies. Using Spearman Rank Order Correlation, the analysis shows that Bed Capacity, Monthly Average Occupancy Rate, and Number of Years Operating are significantly linked to the extent of marketing strategy implementation, indicating a positive relationship. However, the hotel industry's accreditation type does not exhibit significant association with the extent of marketing strategy implementation.

The findings align with research by Liu (2022), who emphasizes the importance of the monthly average occupancy rate as a key performance metric in evaluating hotel operations. A high occupancy rate signifies efficient space utilization and increased revenue generation, reflecting effective hotel management practices. Conversely, a low occupancy rate may highlight areas for improvement and optimization within the hotel's operations and marketing strategies. By considering these factors, hotel managers can make informed decisions to enhance marketing efforts and overall performance.

Table 7. The Profile of the Hotel Industry and the Level of Effectiveness of Marketing Strategies in its Relationship

Variables	rs	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Type of Accreditation	0.021	0.003	Reject	Significant
Bed Capacity	0.033	0.005	Reject	Significant
Monthly average Occupants	0.032	0.032	Reject	Significant
Year of Operation	0.022	0.002	Reject	Significant

Spearman Rank Correlation level of Significant =0.05

Table 7 presents the data in identifying the relationship between the profile of the hotel industry and the level of effectiveness of marketing strategies. Using Spearman Rank Order Correlation, it shows that the Type of Accreditation, Bed Capacity, Monthly Average Occupancy Rate, and Number of Years Operating are significantly related to the level of effectiveness of marketing strategies. This means that there is a positive relationship between these variables.

Table 8. Relationship between the Level of Implementation and the Level of Effectiveness of Marketing Strategies of Hotel Industries in Dumaguete City.

Variables	Coefficients	SE	t Stat	P-Value
Product	601.988	4106.04	0.147	0.884
Price	-10247.981	3537.424	-2.897	0.005
Promotion	6594.353	3147.108	2.095	0.040
Place	6320.275	2809.295	2.25	0.028
R=	0.4604			
R ² =	0.2119			
adjusted R ² =	0.1656			
F-Ratio=	4.572			
p-value=	0.002 (significant)			

Table 8 reveals the level of implementation and effectiveness concerning the four Ps of marketing. Through Multiple Regression Analysis, the overall F Test indicates significance ($p=0.002$), suggesting that some implementations serve as significant predictors of Marketing Strategy Effectiveness. Upon closer examination, the data demonstrate that the implementation of the 4Ps - product ($p=0.884$), price ($p=0.005$), promotion ($p=0.040$), and place ($p=0.028$) - significantly influences the current marketing strategies. Notably, the negative coefficient ($-10,247.981$) associated with price implementation suggests that higher levels of price strategy implementation correspond to lower effectiveness of the strategy. This underscores the impact of pricing strategies on overall effectiveness.

Abrate et al. (2019) emphasize the critical role of appropriate pricing in value and revenue generation, particularly in industries like hospitality where products, such as hotel rooms, are perishable goods. Effective pricing strategies involve setting rates according to temporal profiles to maximize revenues. This aligns with the findings, suggesting that while price implementation is essential, there exists a delicate balance between pricing and strategy effectiveness. By understanding these dynamics, hotel businesses can optimize their pricing strategies to enhance overall marketing effectiveness and revenue generation.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The research provides significant insights into the hotel sector in Dumaguete City, highlighting important patterns and dynamics. A substantial proportion of establishments in the sector are accredited by the Department of Tourism, indicating a strong commitment to maintaining regulatory compliance and quality standards. The study also underscores the hotels' resilience and adaptability in dealing with the challenges posed by the pandemic, evidenced by satisfactory monthly average occupancy rates and moderate bed capacity, which help ensure visitor satisfaction and operational sustainability.

The findings reveal that a significant proportion of hotels have demonstrated durability, suggesting their ability to withstand market fluctuations and adapt to new conditions. The examination of marketing strategy execution shows favorable evaluations for all key elements, with a clear link between a proactive approach and effectiveness. This underscores the importance of innovation and strategic adaptation to optimize outcomes.

Notably, while the type of accreditation does not significantly affect strategy execution, the profile of the hotel industry does influence the efficacy of marketing efforts. This highlights the importance of understanding regional market intricacies and consumer preferences.

Overall, these observations emphasize the critical need for hotels in Dumaguete City to adapt to changing market dynamics and prioritize customer satisfaction. By leveraging these findings, stakeholders can strategically position themselves for long-term success and growth in the region's ever-evolving hospitality industry.

The following are the recommendations

Firstly, establishing a dedicated individual or team within the marketing department to oversee social media strategies is indeed crucial. However, instead of merely checking if strategies are working, this person or team should be responsible for continuously analyzing social media metrics, engaging with customers, and adapting strategies based on performance data. This proactive approach will ensure that the hotel remains agile in addressing market demands and guest preferences in real time.

Secondly, creating a disaster management team is a prudent step, but it should extend beyond marketing methods to encompass overall crisis preparedness and response. This team should consist of cross-functional members who can swiftly adapt strategies during challenging times, whether it's a crisis in the industry or external factors affecting tourism.

Thirdly, networking with other hotels is valuable, but the focus should be on collaboration rather than competition. By forming partnerships with other establishments, hotels in Dumaguete City can leverage each other's strengths, share resources, and collectively promote tourism in the region. This collaborative approach fosters a supportive community and enhances the overall visitor experience.

Lastly, the proposed Marketing Strategy Framework formulated in this study should be followed.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The voluntary participation of managers from various hotels in Dumaguete City is of utmost importance. Participants have the right to withdraw from the study at any point, regardless of their age. Informed consent is a fundamental principle in this study, requiring researchers to provide detailed information and assurances about the nature of the study. This ensures that participants fully understand the implications of their involvement and can make an informed decision freely, without any form of coercion.

Proposed Marketing Strategies Framework

Step 1. Product. Identify Opportunity.

Market on your loyal guests. They are critical to segment and match your products to their demands. Create loyalty programs to encourage customers.

Product Innovation. Align the goods and services with the customers' ever-changing demands and expectations. Smart amenities throughout the facility and thoughtful features let guests fully personalize their stay and create the coziest possible environment.

Understanding your guests. Finding and targeting your ideal guest profile for accurate analysis and customer segmentation.

Step 2. Price. Plan and standardize.

Utilize a dynamic pricing strategy. This is used to dynamically modify the price of their goods or services in response to a range of variables, including supply and demand, the time of day, competition pricing, and consumer behavior. Make sure your pricing captures the special and use storytelling and focused marketing to highlight it.

Consider Variable Pricing. Under a variable pricing approach, a product or service's price varies according to demand. This entails modifying room rates in response to a range of variables, including seasonality, events, and booking trends.

Step 3. Promotion. Measure and implement changes.

Collaborate with other hotels. This will develop integrated learning experiences to network.

Create a Disaster Management Team. This will help your hotel industry emphasize marketing strategies and adjust accordingly before any crisis arises.

Seasonal Promotions: To draw customers and fill empty rooms, provide discounts or unique packages during off-peak seasons. Provide early booking incentives, such as discounts or extra benefits, to entice visitors to make bookings.

Step 4. Place. Evaluate and standardize.

Continuously Monitor and Adopt. To continue to keep your offerings appealing and relevant, stay updated on changes in travel reasons, guest feedback, and market trends.

Continuous Improvement. Remaining competitive and surpassing guest expectations requires listening to feedback, keeping up with industry developments, and upholding operational excellence.

Mobile optimization: To cater to the increasing number of guests who use smartphones and tablets to research and book hotels, make sure your website and booking procedure are mobile-friendly.

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